

Historical Development of Sport and Physical Culture

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Abstract: This paper looks at the history of sport, how it has developed, the changes in its importance to people.

Keywords: Health, sport, physical culture, historical aspects, Olympic Games, development of sport.

Introduction: The key to health and well-being in our lives is motor activity, and it is this activity that forms the basis of physical culture and sport, which in turn consist of a variety of physical exercises and their elements, various competitions and spartakiades. It was with such a concept as "motor activity" that the development of the field of sport and physical culture began, which has now led to the fact that physical culture has come to exist as a separate, independent discipline, which is currently present in the curriculum of schools, colleges and institutions of higher education both in Uzbekistan and abroad.

Throughout time, the course of development of physical culture and sport has changed, and it is through knowledge of the historical aspects of this field that it is possible to influence the further development and future of physical culture and sport by predicting and studying trends. In order to anticipate trends in the development of sport, it is necessary to look at the model of this area in the past, because it is on the basis of this that all subsequent stages of development with the emergence of innovations emerged.

Methods: Speaking about the stages of development of physical culture and sport, it is worth mentioning their multifaceted nature throughout history. Some people found and still find in it a useful pastime, others - excellent physical fitness and military training, and some - a career and growth in this sphere. In the course of development of motor culture various kinds of sports began to appear, some of which gradually underwent changes, and some of which remained unchanged, but there are also those that have ceased to be relevant and disappeared. A striking example of the development of this sphere is the emergence of the Paralympic Games for the disabled and people with disabilities.

Ancient Greece was the territorial origin of sport, and the first Olympic Games were held there in Olympia. Based on scientific literature, the oldest sport is Tavrokotapsia, which is a "game with bulls", during which slaves had to jump over the backs of bulls, holding on to their horns. This sport was considered sacred, as jumping over bulls was a kind of ritual. But not only tavrokotapsia was connected with religiosity, the origin of the Olympic Games originates from a religious ritual, which consisted in running to the altar of Zeus. Thus, the first games were held in 776 BC. It turns out that at that time sport was connected with the beliefs and religious ideas of people, which is why participation in the Olympic Games was considered prestigious, and athletes were respected among the local population. It is worth noting that only men could

participate in the games, women were not allowed.

The most popular competition was pankration - fighting without rules, at the moment, it is mixed martial arts. There were others: horse racing, pentathlon, discus throwing and others. In time, activities of this kind also appeared in Rome. The relevance of sports gradually grew and in time there was a concept that exists to this day - "athlete". People of this category occupied a higher place in the social ladder among the population, and this kind of activity was considered as prestigious as in ancient Greece. The role of physical culture was not only in the development of sports activities, but also in the military - physical training of the army, which were conducted in the field and military camps.

Speaking about Ancient Rome and Greece, it is possible to tell about existence of a cult of a perfect body and athletic physique. There was a special attitude to the physical development of man, his coherence and beauty. All these qualities were demonstrated at the Olympic Games. Along with this important aspect was intellectual development. Thus, a person had to be well developed both physically and mentally. Speaking of sports, their main feature was spectacularity.

Over time, views on physical education and sport began to change, the first fundamental moment being the fall of Rome. The first fundamental moment was the fall of Rome, after which people's religious beliefs changed, as well as their overall outlook on many aspects of life. The centre of attention was now the soul of a person, not his appearance. For people, God was at the centre of everything, and with him the afterlife. All the activities and thoughts of medieval people under the influence of the church were directed towards moral qualities and spiritual peace. So, the human body began to acquire the meaning of any sin, and together with it the denial of ideas of ancient Greeks and Romans about physical superiority began. At that time, sport was used for one purpose only. It became a tool for creation of well-trained warriors of church with developed physical qualities. At this stage sport and physical culture were in regression.

As time passed, the Middle Ages changed to the Modern Age and the development of physical education and sport changed its course. The influence of the church gradually began to wane, and in parallel with this, the attitudes of society began to change again. Now a person is aimed at contemplation of beautiful things and self-improvement in all directions, including knowledge of politics, economics and other areas. Physical training and sport became relevant again, and with it hygiene was developed for the first time. At this time there are hints of current sports in several countries and national competitions appear. This makes it necessary to create certain rules for their conduct. Thus, sport regained its aesthetic significance and also became a leisure activity.

The next stage in the development of physical culture and sport took place in the early 19th century, which is characterised by industrialisation. Thanks to this, railways appeared, which had a favourable effect on sports - players in teams could travel to various competitions. At that time, the Industrial Revolution takes place, due to which most of the rural population gradually moves to the cities. People were becoming more urbanised and sport was becoming an integral part of these cities. This was the time when sports spectators - fans - emerged, who chose their favourite among the teams.

People who were passionate about sports started to unite into sports communities and parallel to this, sports clubs started to emerge. Some sports became so ingrained in people's lives that they became an element of culture and a symbol of a particular country. For example, lacrosse and hockey in Canada and baseball in the United States. It is during this time period that sports and physical culture begin to be seen as a motivation to develop a person's inner qualities. It becomes a strong tool in self-development, thus the educational and pedagogical value appears. At this time, physical culture acquired the significance of an independent discipline

and appeared in the curriculum.

But there is a negative moment in the development of sport - the emergence of doping. Of course, it has existed throughout time, starting from the times of Ancient Greece. But at that time they used products of plant origin, which by today's standards are the easiest and safest for the human body. Later, caffeine was also used as an invigorating and tonic substance.

With the advent of the 20th century, not only sports, but also one of the sciences - chemistry - was developed. In this regard, experiments in the creation of various drugs with stimulating effect began. To obtain the highest results, some athletes began to use various kinds of additives. The use of synthetic supplements caused the emergence of anti-doping campaigns and programmes. Thus, the use of doping by an athlete meant his disqualification.

Results and Discussion: The sport received the biggest boost in development during the Modern period. At the moment, it is used for career building, health and youth, psychotherapy, physical and military training, etc.

Conclusion: Analysing the history of sport makes it clear that along with the development of this sphere, mankind itself developed. Starting with ritual jumps, with each stage physical culture acquired a new meaning, and with it the attitude to one's own physical form changed. Sport became one of the ways to one's own self-development and perfection. Developing both physical and inner qualities of a person, it is an excellent tool for maintaining the balance between body and soul.

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